

region 1020-1070 cm^{-1} , $\Delta\nu$ for the complex were 0 to +9 cm^{-1} and confirmed the C=S assignment of the bands. As the C-O-C frequencies of the complex are expected to be higher than the alkali xanthate, the absorption frequencies of the complex at 1275 and 1260 cm^{-1} may be attributed to C-O-C linkage.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Late Prof. H. N. Khastgir, Head of the Department of Chemistry, University of North Bengal for extending full laboratory facilities.

References

1. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Orient Longmans, London, 1969.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Orient Longmans, London, 1969.
3. L. H. LITTLE, G. W. POLING and J. LIJA, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1961, **39**, 745.
4. L. H. LITTLE, G. W. POLING and J. LIJA, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1961, **39**, 1783.

Chemical Constituents of the Flowers of *Strobilanthes callosus* (Acanthaceae)

M. ILYAS*, (MISS) RANJANA VERMA and (MISS)
PARVEEN JAMAL

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh—202001

Manuscript received 26 July 1978, revised 4 December 1978,
accepted 21 December 1978

STROBILANTHES callosus Nees, is a herb having yellowish flowers with spikes and panicles. In India plant is commonly known as Karvi. Flowers and leaves are used for different purposes¹⁻². No chemical studies have so far been reported on this plant.

Air dried flowers were extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°). The concentrated extract was divided into acidic and neutral fraction by usual method. The neutral fraction on column chromatography over neutral alumina gave four different substances marked A, B, C, and D.

The GLC analysis of the substance A m.p. 62-67° over 3% SE 30 column at 250° showed it to be a mixture of n-alkanes containing hentriacontane (36.3%), tritriacontane (28.9%), nonacosane (21.2%), dotriacontane (4.5%) and triacontane (2.9%), heptacosane (2.0%), hexatriacontane (1.5%), tetratriacontane (1.0%), octacosane (1.0%) accompanied by hexacosane, pentacosane, and pentatriacontane as a minor constituent. Fraction B m.p. 79-80° was classified as saturated alcohol by I.R.

and Co-TLC. GLC analysis showed it to be a mixture of n-alcohols containing tetratriacontanol (40.5%), dotriacontanol (30.5%), tritriacontanol (20.8%), triacontanol (4.3%), hentriacontanol (3.6%). Nonacosanol, pentatriacontanol, and hexatriacontanol was also found as a trace constituent.

The compound C m.p. 210° gave positive Liebermann Burchard and Noller's test. I.R., m.p., m.m.p. and Co-TLC showed it to be lupeol. Compound D m.p. was identified as sterol by Liebermann Burchard and Noller's test. GC-MS analysis³ showed it to be a mixture of four sterols. Cholesterol (0.4%) (M^+ 458), campesterol (11.0%) (M^+ 472), stigmasterol (41.5%) (M^+ 484) and β -sitosterol (47.0%) (M^+ 486).

The acidic fraction contains mainly saturated fatty acids m.p. 65°. GLC analysis at 250° showed it to be a mixture of C_{24} - C_{30} fatty acids; pentacosanoic acid (54.0%), heptacosanoic acid (22.5%), nonacosanoic acid (8.5%), hexacosanoic acid (6.2%), octacosanoic acid (3.5%), pentatriacontanoic acid (2.6%) and hentriacontanoic acid (2.3%) along with the minor quantities of triacontanoic acid and heptatriacontanoic acid.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (R.V.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of J.R.F.

References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAVAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R. (India), 1956, p. 235.
2. K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU, "Indian Medicinal Plants", 1918, p. 958.
3. J. A. BALLANTINE, R. C. ROBERTS and R. J. MORRIS, *J. Chromatog.*, 1975, **103**, 289.

Base Adducts of Bis (Acetylacetonato) Zinc(II) with Nitrogen Donors

C. D. RAO, D. SATYANARAYANA and B. K. MOHAPATRA
Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack 753 008

Manuscript received 29 May 1978, revised 19 October 1978,
accepted 3 November 1978

LEWIS acid behaviour of metal chelates of β -diketones and related compounds which involve keto-enol tautomerism have invoked lot of interest in recent years. Stability of β -diketonates has been partly explained on the basis of benzenoid resonance¹ and reactions characteristic of aromatic system have been carried out²⁻⁴ on metal β -diketonates to provide further evidence regarding the aromaticity. We have been trying for the adduct formation of metal β -diketonates with heterocyclic bases and isolated a number adducts of Zinc(II)⁵⁻⁷ and Copper(II)^{8,9} β -diketonates with

heterocyclic amines. This communication reports some complexes of the composition $[\text{Zn}(\text{ac. ac})_2\text{L}]$, where L is diethylamine, triethylamine, diethylenediamine, triphenylamine and 4-cyanopyridine.

Experimental

Bis acetylacetonato Zinc(II) was prepared by a previously known method⁵ by treating an ethanolic solution of zinc chloride with acetylacetonone in stoichiometric ratio followed by dropwise addition of ammonia. The precipitated compound was filtered, washed with ethanol, followed by ether and dried in *vacuo*. Analysis of the compound corresponded to the composition $[\text{Zn}(\text{ac. ac})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$. The IR spectrum of this compound showed an absorption band at 3450 cm^{-1} attributable to coordinated water.

Preparation of the Complexes: A warm methanolic solution of bis (acetylacetonato) zinc monohydrate was treated with each of the ligands in 1:2 ratio and refluxed for two hours. Crystalline compounds separated out after keeping the resulting clear solutions for one or two days. These were filtered, washed with ethanol, followed by ether and dried in *vacuum*.

These are white crystalline, have low melting points and are fairly soluble in acetone in which medium they behave as nonelectrolytes, the Δ_M values being in the order of 8-11 mhos. cm^2 . The characteristic band at 3450 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum of the monohydrate due to coordinated water is absent and hence it appears that this water molecule is replaced by one of the reacting ligands maintaining penta-coordination⁵.

The infrared spectra of these complexes are informative. Bands that can be assigned¹⁰ to (C=C) and (C=O) stretching frequencies along with other assignments are listed in Table 2 to indicate the shifts that are brought about in these bands due to introduction of a nitrogen ligand. Even though it is difficult unambiguously to ascertain the direction of shift in C=C and C=O absorption bands since the extent of combined effect of σ - and π -bonding is uncertain, definite shifts in (C=C), (C=O), (M-O) and ligand absorption frequencies, together with the presence of metal ligand absorption bands, provide evidence for bonding of the amines to the β -diketonate and the presence of pentacoordinated zinc.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, MELTING POINT, CONDUCTANCE DATA OF ZINC(II) COMPLEXES

Compounds	M.P. (°C)	Conductance (mhos. cm^2)	% Zinc		% Nitrogen	
			Found	Calc	Found	Calc
$\text{Zn}(\text{ac. ac})_2$ triethylamine	160	8.5	17.65	17.94	9.6	2.84
$\text{Zn}(\text{ac. ac})_2$ triphenylamine	185	6.4	12.62	12.86	2.5	2.75
$\text{Zn}(\text{ac. ac})_2$ diethylenediamine	170	10.0	18.56	18.71	7.86	8.01
$\text{Zn}(\text{ac. ac})_2$ (4-cyanopyridine)	170	7.5	17.48	17.79	7.2	7.62
$\text{Zn}(\text{ac. ac})_2$ diethylamine	176	10.5	19.15	19.43	9.9	4.16

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRA* OF ZINC(II) COMPLEXES (cm^{-1})

Compound	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O}) + \delta(\text{C}-\text{H})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{L})$
Acetylacetonone	1628 S	1553 S	1500 m	—	—
$[\text{Zn}(\text{ac. ac})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	1605 S	1535 S	1480 m	420 m	—
$[\text{Zn}(\text{ac. ac})_2\text{L}]$ where L is :					
Triethylamine	1610 VS	1540 S	1490 S	425 m	380 m
Triphenylamine	1605 VS	1520 S	1495 S	430 m	385 m
Diethylenediamine	1610 VS	1530 S	1490 S	425 m	380 m
4-Cyanopyridine	1610 S	1535 S	1480 S	435 m	385 m
Diethylamine	1615 S	1540 S	1490 S	425 m	385 m

* Some of the ligand bands coincide with the assigned bands given here.

Conductance measurements were carried out in M/1000 acetone solution. Presence of nitrogen ligands in the products was established by running IR spectra of the compounds (as nujol mulls). Melting point, analysis and conductance data are recorded in Table 1 and spectral data in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes reported in the present investigation have the composition $[\text{Zn}(\text{ac. ac})_2\text{L}]$.

References

1. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003.
2. P. R. SINGH and R. SAHAI, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 699.
3. P. R. SINGH and R. SAHAI, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 649.
4. P. R. SINGH and R. SAHAI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta.*, 1968, **2**, 102.
5. B. K. MOHAPATRA and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1970, **372**, 332.
6. B. K. MOHAPATRA, and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *Inorg. Chem. Acta.*, 1970, **4**, 404.

7. B. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 3923.
8. B. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 3930.
9. B. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1973, **315**, 347.
10. K. NAKAMOTO, *Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds*, (Wiley, New York), 1963, p. 224.

Studies on Tartrato-Aquo Lead(II) and Its Substituted Derivatives

D. C. DAS and S. PANI,

Department of Chemistry, Sambalpur University,
Jyoti Vihar, Burla.

Manuscript received 9 November 1977, revised 25 September 1978,
accepted 3 November 1978

BOBTELSKY and Graus¹ have reported the formation of insoluble lead tartrate $Pb_2C_4H_2O_6$ which transforms to $PbC_4H_4O_6$ at pH 8.5 and dissolves between pH 4 and 5. Panova² reported the increase in solubility of lead tartrate with increasing tartrate concentration at constant pH and was attributed to the formation of complex containing two tartrate ligands. A further survey of the literature reveals that there is no systematic study on the synthesis and characterization of lead(II) tartrate. As a part of our study on the synthesis of tartrate salts of different metal ions, we report the preparation and properties of lead(II) tartrate and a few of its derivatives in this communication.

Experimental

Analar (B.D.H.) quality chemicals were used. Lead(II) tartrate was prepared from an equimolar solution of lead nitrate and sodium potassium tartrate. The compound is almost insoluble in water, but is soluble in strong bases like sodium hydroxide, potassium hydroxide and also in aqueous ammonia, methyl, ethyl and other aliphatic amines. The evaporation of a saturated solution of lead tartrate in sodium hydroxide yields a compound of composition $Na PbT(OH) \cdot 4H_2O$, where T=tartrate ion. A similar compound, $K PbT(OH)$ is obtained from saturated solution in potassium hydroxide. These compounds are soluble in water and hydrolysed in dilute solution. The compounds similarly obtained from aqueous ammonia and amine solution are

insoluble in water and have composition $PbTR$, where R=ammonia or amine (Table 1).

The estimation of lead and nitrogen have been done respectively by sulphate and micro Kjeldahl's methods and that of tartrate by the procedure reported earlier³.

TABLE 1

Compounds	%Calculated			%Found		
	Pb	T	N	Pb	T	N
$PbT \cdot H_2O$	55.52	39.72	—	55.56	39.76	—
$K PbT(OH)$	50.41	35.99	—	51.82	34.86	—
$Na PbT(OH) \cdot 4H_2O$	44.39	31.67	—	45.39	32.12	—
$PbTNH_3$	55.69	39.77	3.76	54.78	37.89	3.43
$PbTNH_3CH_3$	53.67	38.32	3.62	52.32	37.58	3.21
$PbTN(CH_3)_3$	50.03	34.82	3.34	51.12	35.73	3.12
$PbTNH_3C_2H_5$	51.75	37.1	3.5	52.32	36.8	3.2
$PbTNH(C_2H_5)_3$	48.36	34.58	3.27	49.53	32.93	3.06
$PbTN(C_2H_5)_3$	45.37	32.45	3.07	47.21	30.36	2.89

The i.r. spectra of $PbT \cdot H_2O$, $PbT \cdot NH_3$ and $PbT \cdot N(CH_3)_3$ were taken in potassium bromide phase, and some of the absorption bands are collected in Table 2.

Discussion

In sodium potassium tartrate, one strong and one weak band are observed at 1620 cm^{-1} and 1455 cm^{-1} respectively which are due to symmetrical and antisymmetrical vibration of the carboxylate groups whereas in d-tartaric acid, the sharp band at 1750 cm^{-1} and 1097 cm^{-1} have been assigned to the free carboxylic acid group and C=O stretching frequency of secondary alcoholic group respectively⁴.

In $PbTH_2O$, $PbT \cdot NH_3$ and $PbTN(CH_3)_3$ strong bands are found at 1560 , 1580 and 1556 cm^{-1} respectively, but no bands are observed either at 1620 cm^{-1} , 1455 cm^{-1} and 1750 cm^{-1} . This large shift indicates strong coordination of both the carboxylate groups with the metal atom. Goulden⁵ has reported that in lactate ion the secondary alcoholic group has an in-plane bending absorption band at 1275 cm^{-1} which shifts to 1390 cm^{-1} on chelation with zinc. In sodium potassium tartrate, there is a band at about 1240 cm^{-1} which might be due to in-plane O-H bonding of secondary alcoholic groups. In these compounds, strong bands are observed at 1380 - 1375 cm^{-1} and weak bands at 1250 - 1260 cm^{-1} . These results indicate that one

TABLE 2

Compounds	Absorption band in cm^{-1}
$PbT \cdot OH$,	1560(s), 1375(s), 1125(m), 1075(m), 595(w), 510(w), 380
$PbT \cdot NH_3$,	1580(s), 1380(s), 1130(m), 1094(m), 590(w), 500(w), 400, 372
$PbTN(CH_3)_3$,	1556(s), 1375(s), 1125(m), 1070(m), 595(w), 505(w), 430, 390
Sodium Potassium tartrate	1620(s), 1455(w), 1240, 1110, 1060